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A PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR DEVELOPING SECONDARY SCHOOL CURRICULA IN THE KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA IN LIGHT OF THE GLOBAL TREND TOWARD INTERNATIONALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop a proposed framework for improving secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in light of the global trend toward internationalization of education. To achieve this aim, a list of topics related to internationalization of education was prepared, along with a checklist to determine the degree to which these topics are embedded in the curricula. The researcher employed the descriptive-analytical method as it is appropriate to the objectives of the study. The study sample consisted of 110 secondary-school teachers in Al-Kharj Governorate. The findings indicated that the weighted mean for the degree of inclusion of internationalization-of-education topics in secondary school curricula, from the teachers' perspective, was 2.09, with a standard deviation of 0.808; according to the Likert scale adopted, this represents a "moderate" level. The results further showed that there were no statistically significant differences at the ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level in respondents' views regarding the inclusion of internationalization topics in secondary curricula attributable to the variables of academic qualification or years of experience. In light of these findings, a proposed framework was presented for embedding internationalization-of-education topics in school curricula. Based on the results, the study offered a set of recommendations and suggestions for future research.

KEYWORDS: *proposed framework; curriculum development; internationalization of education; secondary stage.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The current era has seen a significant increase in interconnectedness among nations in all aspects of life, particularly in the academic and knowledge spheres. This has been driven by several factors, chief among which is globalization, which has necessitated for education and its various institutions greater mutual understanding, solidarity, and shared responsibility. Consequently, these institutions have adopted the philosophy of internationalization, which is based on a shift from a narrow, local framework to a broader, global one that integrates international, cultural, and global dimensions into the education system.

According to Al-Buhy (2014), the concept of the internationalization of education emerged due to the rapid global advancements in technology, science, and military capabilities, leading to increased global interaction

among nations and making the world seem like a global village. The emergence of international organizations also played a role, enacting regulations allowing for intervention in the domestic affairs of nations in various areas, including education and pedagogy.

According to Childress (2019), there is a growing global trend toward the internationalization of education, aiming to achieve international, cultural, and global integration to prevent a clash of civilizations. This is set against the backdrop of powers, alliances, and conflicts between civilizations, creating a state of anxiety, tension, and global instability, particularly in the wake of the “clash of civilizations” theory.

Al-'Ani (2022) suggests that the internationalization of education, also known as the globalization of education, entails preparing the global citizen. This involves integrating educational systems, curricula, and content globally to address contemporary technological, economic, and cultural challenges and promote international understanding and cooperation. The trend has garnered significant support among education specialists, who advocate for the globalization of education and its implementation, provided that local cultural identity is preserved and its benefits are maximized.

Al-Jammal (2024) highlights that the internationalization of education encompasses various educational stages and domains, including student exchanges, study-abroad programs, and curriculum cooperation. This internationalization fosters mutual and balanced international mobility among education systems through a set of mechanisms and activities that serve as its key foundations.

Notable countries that have prioritized the internationalization of education include the United States of America, China, Japan, India, Singapore, and Korea. These nations have emphasized education quality, teacher preparation, highlighted national, cultural, and value-based aspects, leveraged technological advancements, and aligned education with future labor market needs, making them attractive destinations for international students and researchers and placing them at the forefront of global rankings (Subrata, 2010).

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has demonstrated a clear interest in the internationalization of education through its Vision 2030, which prioritizes international cooperation in education. Vision 2030 has launched the Strategic Partnerships Program, aiming to position the Kingdom as a hub connecting three continents by competing for global leadership and elevating education to world-class standards at all stages and in all its domains (Al-Yami, 2018).

Talabah and Al-Otaibi (2028) highlight the Kingdom's efforts, noting its prominent role in developing its educational system through strategic partnerships with international educational institutions in scientific research, field visits, academic networking, and knowledge exchange. The goal is to prepare a global citizen who understands change, confronts challenges, and possesses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable openness to the world and contribution to solving its problems and issues, while preserving a distinctive national and Islamic identity.

Although the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia emphasizes the internationalization of education across various stages, secondary education requires special attention. According to Al-Khalifah (2017), the secondary stage is a gateway to university education or the labor market, playing a crucial role in preparing citizens. This stage also coincides with a critical period in young people's lives, marked by changes in structure, cognition, and behavior, necessitating self-building and forming a well-balanced personality.

Faraj (2018) notes that these goals are primarily achieved through the curricula offered at this stage. School curricula are a core element in secondary education, defining the framework that guides the educational process and contributing to achieving its objectives; therefore, these curricula must respond to the global trend toward the internationalization of education.

Hassan (2013) emphasizes that curricula are the foundation of education and the teaching–learning process, and key factors in shaping individual abilities. Curricula are a means to achieving higher objectives, not an end in themselves, such as developing thinking processes, global outlook, and meeting societal needs; therefore, curricula must be developed to keep pace with societal change.

Mahmud and 'Abd Al-Hadi (2025) highlight the need to integrate global and cultural dimensions into secondary education to graduate globally thinking students. This includes aligning curricula with

international standards, student exchanges, foreign expertise, global skills, and flexible systems like the dual system to link education with labor markets. Research emphasizes the importance of developing curricula in light of global education and internationalization (Abu Faraj, 2019; Al-Dusuqi, 2019; Al-Sheha, 2023; Chong, 2025). Abu Faraj (2019) highlighted constructing curricula in light of global challenges. Al-Dusuqi (2019) recommended redesigning curricula for global citizenship. Al-Shehah (2023) stressed globalization of education and curricula development for global citizenship. Chong (2025) recommended addressing global education dimensions in curricula.

Thus, internationalizing secondary curricula in KSA requires efforts to examine the incorporation of internationalization topics, assess their "globalness", and propose a developmental framework to achieve desired goals.

Research Problem Awareness

The awareness of the research problem emerged from several sources, most notably:

1. Criticisms of school curricula. Research (Musa, 2014; Al-Nassar, 2016; Al-Shehri and Al-Juaid, 2020; Al-Amer, 2024) indicates that secondary curricula are traditional, detached from local and global requirements, focus on quantity over quality, theoretical over practical, and disconnected from students' needs and labor market. Current curricula can't prepare youth for global competition and excellence.

2. Previous Research Recommendations

Research (Al-Atiyyah, 2010; Al-Darij, 2018; Subrata, 2020; 'Abd Al-Majid, 2021; Muhammad, 2022; Raslan, 2022; 'Ali, 2023; Elnagar & Young, 2025) recommends reforming secondary curricula as a fundamental pillar of educational reform. To establish modern education shaping tomorrow's human being, equipped with nation's constants, creative skills, analytical abilities, universal orientations, and modernity values, enabling learners to interact with the age, excel, and contribute to nation building.

3. Educational writings by Carnoy (2010), 'Abd Al-Hay (2013), and Al-Jammal (2024) have highlighted the importance of the internationalization of education, seeing it as a necessity for enhancing global competitiveness, building human capital qualified for the labor market, improving the quality of education through international exchange of expertise, developing global thinking skills and intercultural collaboration, and attracting talent and research. This, in turn, enhances countries' standing, creates economic and innovative opportunities, and contributes to sustainable development.
4. Responding to international calls and global and local transformations, the secondary education system is tasked with qualifying students and training them in diverse skills, aligning secondary education outputs with labor market requirements, and achieving excellence and competitiveness on the global stage. This is accomplished by integrating global and cultural dimensions, international comparisons, and digital technologies into education's content, methods, and aims, enhancing global competencies, employability skills, and broadening students' horizons (Al-owda et al., 2024).
5. The researcher's review of certain secondary-school curricula revealed a lack of coverage of topics related to the internationalization of education, including the international dimension, global concepts, global diversity, and civilizational interaction. Students' evident weakness in these areas stems from the absence or weak representation of such topics in the curriculum, which needs strengthening.
6. Consultations with education experts indicate a need to incorporate topics related to the internationalization of education into secondary-school curricula, enhancing competitiveness and meeting global labor market demands. This would lead to graduating cadres capable of innovation and holistic thinking, supporting the country's economic growth and bolstering its international standing.

Defining the research problem:

The present study addresses the lack of internationalization-of-education topics in secondary-school curricula. This necessitates an educational intervention to develop these curricula and integrate internationalization-of-education topics. The main research question is:

What is the proposed framework for integrating the internationalization of education into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?

Research questions:

1. What internationalization-of-education topics should be incorporated into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?
2. To what extent are internationalization-of-education topics currently included in secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, from teachers' perspectives?
3. Are there statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the sample's responses regarding the inclusion of internationalization-of-education topics in secondary-school curricula, attributable to academic qualification and years of experience?
4. What is the proposed framework for integrating internationalization-of-education topics into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?

Research aims:

The present study aims to:

1. Identify internationalization-of-education topics to be incorporated into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
2. Determine the extent to which internationalization-of-education topics are currently included in secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, from teachers' perspectives.
3. Examine differences in the sample's responses regarding the inclusion of internationalization-of-education topics in secondary-school curricula, attributable to academic qualification and years of experience.
4. Develop a proposed framework for integrating internationalization-of-education topics into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Significance of the study:

This study has the following benefits:

Theoretical significance:

The study enriches the Arabic library with a specialized work on the internationalization of education at the secondary stage, addressing the scarcity of Arabic studies in this field.

Applied significance:

The study benefits:

- **Students:** by developing their skills and abilities in light of the internationalization of education.
- **Teachers:** by providing a proposed framework for developing school curricula.
- **Curriculum designers:** by offering a list of global topics related to the internationalization of education for secondary-school curricula.
- **Researchers:** by opening avenues for further research on curriculum development and the internationalization of education at different educational stages.

Research methodology:

The present study employed the descriptive-analytical method. This approach was used to:

- Develop the theoretical framework.

- Survey relevant educational literature and previous Arabic and foreign research on the study variables.
- Describe the procedures for developing the study materials and instruments.

Study Boundaries:

The study is limited to:

- **Topic:** Internationalization of education, and the content of secondary-school curricula.
- **Participants:** secondary-school teachers.
- **Time:** the 2025–2026 academic year.
- **Location:** secondary schools in Al-Kharj Governorate, KSA.

Study terms:

In light of the theoretical background presented in this study, its key terms are defined operationally as follows:

- **Internationalization of education:** The integration of topics with international, global, and cultural dimensions into secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, to make them more open and internationally competitive, and provide students with skills and knowledge for success in an interconnected world, while preserving cultural identity.
- **Curriculum development:** A systematic process involving procedures and steps to introduce modifications and improvements to secondary-school curricula in light of internationalization-of-education topics, to keep pace with scientific and educational developments and international changes, enhancing the efficiency of the educational process and meeting the needs of the learner and society.
- **Secondary stage:** The final stage of general education, targeting students aged 15-18 years, with a duration of three years, characterized by a tracks system.
- **Proposed framework:** A forward-looking plan setting out a vision for improving secondary-school curricula in light of internationalization-of-education topics, to ensure they keep pace with international changes and meet the needs of learners and society.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

The study's theoretical framework covers two main areas:

- Internationalization of Education.
- Secondary Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Detailed discussion follows.

First Axis: Internationalization of Education

The rapid global changes and challenges have made it necessary to adopt the internationalization of education to exchange educational expertise and promote education for international understanding. Any education system that distances itself from internationalization will be unable to face, excel in, and compete within the contemporary global context.

Meaning of Internationalization of Education, The term "internationalization" corresponds to the Arabic term "*tadwīl*". Linguistically, it refers to cooperation among states, where countries benefit from collective action (Al-'Amri, 2012). In the Vocabulary Dictionary "*Qāmūs Al-Mufradāt*", "*tadwīl*" is a verbal noun derived from "*dawwala*", meaning to give something an international character or supervision (Al-Buraq, 2025).

Given the importance of the internationalization of education, numerous definitions have been proposed that describe its components and role.

- Dinesh (2010): A way for a country to respond to globalization while respecting its individuality.
- Al-Dajdaj (2016): Integrating a global perspective into educational institutions through activities like scholarships and research collaborations.
- Knight (2018): Integrating an international dimension into an institution's goals, functions, and services.

- Wen and Zhou (2020): A developmental process to face international competition and achieve an international dimension in teaching and research.
- 'Abd Al-qadir (2022): Imparting an international dimension to teaching, research, and community service.

These definitions highlight the shift from local to international education, and openness to external expertise and resources to acquire an international character.

Origin of the Internationalization of Education

The internationalization of education is not a recent concept; it dates back to ancient civilizations. Those who trace ancient Arab civilizations before the advent of Islam find that Quraysh's engagement in trade journeys to Yemen and the Levant in the winter and summer had a significant impact on their interaction with various peoples, cultures, and bodies of knowledge. They became acquainted with the achievements and civilizations of the surrounding world. In Islamic civilization, scholars played a major role in transmitting civilizations, and for several centuries Europe relied heavily on the scientific and intellectual output of Muslim scholars ('Abd Al-Hafiz & 'Abd Al-Mutajalli, 2022).

As Al-Hawali (2023) notes, the early precursors of the movement toward internationalization began with the emergence of educational institutions in the Middle Ages, which sought to imbue their activities with an international dimension. These institutions opened their doors to all seekers of knowledge, facilitated the mobility of professors and students among educational institutions without restrictions, unified the language of instruction, and offered curricula, study programs, and academic degrees that were largely similar—all with the aim of exchanging knowledge and ideas and building bridges of cooperation among themselves.

In the 1970s and 1980s, international attention to the internationalization of education witnessed a major upsurge in response to the effects of globalization. This period was marked by:

- Enhanced role of the European Commission in research, education, and development within the EU.
- Emergence of programs like Erasmus, facilitating student mobility within the EU.

With the 1995 GATS agreement, global education partnerships emerged, and institutions became more international. Key developments included:

- Late 1990s: Several countries joined the EU; Bologna Declaration enabled graduate mobility across Europe.
- 2001: Lisbon Agenda launched to boost European education's global competitiveness (Ayoubi, 2013).

As globalization accelerated, trends shifted toward:

- Cross-border education programs.
- Technology-driven new educational institutions.
- Diversified goals, cultures, and interests spanning global continents (Marginson, 2020).

Justifications for the Internationalization of Education

The studies of Ramaswamy et al. (2021) and 'Abd-Alkarim (2022) highlight multiple justifications for internationalizing education, driven by varied definitions and global attention. Key justifications include:

- National strategies aligning education with local and global labor market needs.
- Competition among institutions for students, researchers, and faculty, and exporting expertise.
- Enhancing global knowledge, skills, and languages for better professional and social performance.
- Economic growth, competitiveness, and knowledge-economy linkage.
- Opening new labor market horizons through economic growth.
- Increased financial incentives from internationalization activities.
- Education's role in preserving cultural identity amid globalization challenges.

These justifications drive developed countries to adopt internationalization. In Saudi Arabia, Vision 2030 aims to make educational institutions leading destinations by:

- Expanding international education reach.
- Attracting global students via scholarships.
- Strengthening foreign institution partnerships.
- Establishing international collaborations.
- Developing modern programs like blended learning for global competitiveness (Al-Beez, 2022).

Objectives and Importance of the Internationalization of Education

The importance of internationalization of education, as Mabrouk (2022) notes, lies in its role in:

- Facing rapid change.
- Increasing competitiveness.
- Achieving global leadership.

Imparting an international character to education's philosophy, outputs, and processes is key to addressing challenges.

Mutinda and Liu (2025) indicate internationalization is:

- A necessity driven by contemporary demands.
- An effective component of academic development.
- A response to local, regional, and global needs.
- A means to graduate capable minds.

Qasim and Salem (2022) outline main objectives:

- Confront local and global changes.
- Improve education quality.
- Enhance global competitiveness and standing.
- Promote cultural exchange.
- Prepare students for the global market.
- Achieve sustainable development.
- Solve global problems.

In addition, and based on a review of other studies and writings (Hajji, 2012; Shields, 2020; Subrata, 2020; 'Abd Al-Qadir, 2022; Asogwa, 2024), the objectives and importance of the internationalization of education can be addressed as follows:

- Improving the quality of education and scientific research so as to meet international standards.
- Producing graduates who are qualified to enter the labor market at the international level.
- Adding and embedding an international dimension within educational institutions in order to enhance their ability to compete globally.
- Promoting tolerance, psychological openness, and acceptance of the "other" in support of global peace and coexistence.
- Mobilizing scientific capacities to provide solutions to the challenges facing societies—economic, social, environmental, and health-related—through research and international cooperation.
- Integrating international, cultural, and global dimensions into the education system in order to enhance its quality and competitiveness.
- Training graduates in contemporary trends that increase employment opportunities in the global labor market.
- Exchanging information, expertise, and knowledge among countries and leveraging their application.
- Helping educational institutions to achieve advanced positions in international rankings.
- Making education both "structure" and "substance" through concerted efforts among nations.
- Providing opportunities for students and faculty members to engage with different cultures.
- Achieving comprehensive development of educational systems and strategies in order to eradicate low educational standards at the local and regional levels.
- Fostering competition among educational institutions with a global profile.

- Enhancing learners' capabilities through global programs and courses that broaden their international employment prospects.

Taken together, these objectives underscore the importance of adopting the internationalization of education within educational institutions, particularly through integrating international, cultural, and global dimensions into the education system to improve its quality and competitiveness. Such integration can contribute to building conscious global citizens, strengthening intercultural understanding, and preparing students for a global labor market.

Types of Internationalization of Education

Jon and Yoo (2021) indicate that there are two basic patterns of policies and programs for the internationalization of education:

- **External Internationalization:** This refers to cooperation among educational institutions across national borders, through activities such as student and faculty exchanges, establishing institutional branches abroad, or providing educational services and outputs outside the home country under international cooperation agreements and partnerships. It represents academic mobility for students, faculty, academic programs, and the institutions themselves.

- **Internal Internationalization:** This involves imparting an international character to curricula and teaching methods, as well as admitting students, researchers, and faculty members from other countries and benefiting from their presence within the institution.

Building on its objectives, the present study focuses on internal internationalization by giving secondary-school curricula an international orientation through linking them to global topics, events, and issues. This is intended to enhance students' understanding of the world, raise their awareness of global issues, and develop their competitive skills and capabilities, while preserving their local identity.

Second Axis: Secondary Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Secondary education is a crucial stage because its graduates are directly connected to higher education on the one hand, and because it is a key factor in shaping students' futures on the other. It serves as a gateway for a new generation seeking its role in society, its future, and the opportunities available to it.

- Al-Khatib (2020) affirms this, noting the importance of secondary education in guiding students in line with their needs and interests in a way that is consistent with the needs and priorities of society.
- Developed countries place particular emphasis on the impact of secondary education in achieving their strategies and future plans.
- This has prompted many of them to diversify secondary education and its structures so that it includes both general and vocational education, and even to diversify the courses studied at this stage through elective tracks that meet students' needs and respond to the evolving requirements of society.

Efforts of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in Secondary Education

Secondary education in the Kingdom has undergone a series of reforms and developments since 1974, when the comprehensive secondary system, based on the credit-hour system, was adopted as the first serious attempt to enhance the efficiency and quality of this stage.

- In 1985, a decision was issued to implement the "Developed Secondary" system, which relies on credit hours and a cumulative GPA, in order to address the problems and drawbacks encountered in the comprehensive secondary system.
- This system was discontinued in 1992 due to implementation shortcomings, and schools reverted to the traditional secondary system until 2005, when a decision was made to implement the "Credit System" in response to social changes and the demands of comprehensive development plans.
- The credit system was introduced in a number of schools and then gradually expanded, followed by the introduction of a developed educational system—the "Semester System"—in 2014 as an alternative to the traditional annual system, alongside the continued application of the credit system.

- During this period, the semester system paralleled the credit system in terms of quality rather than quantity, which had characterized the traditional system (Al-Khath'ami, 2022; Dalil Munsiq Al-Masārāt, 2021).

In pursuit of continuous improvement and development of secondary education, and as part of its contribution to achieving Saudi Vision 2030, the Ministry of Education introduced the “Tracks System,” which was approved at the beginning of the 2021/2022 academic year through the implementation of the first year of secondary education in all public and private schools.

The Tracks System is based on a renewed philosophy that expands opportunities and student participation; it prepares students for life and for continuing their education after secondary school, while also giving them the opportunity to participate in the labor market (Route Coordinator's Guide, 2021).

Although these efforts demonstrate the Kingdom's strong interest in the secondary stage, greater emphasis is still needed on the development of its curricula. This stage is characterized by a set of important features that require those responsible for the educational system to translate them into educational and academic programs that both fulfill national aspirations and absorb and engage with successful global trends and challenges.

Development of Secondary-School Curricula

The importance of developing secondary-school curricula stems from the significance of this stage itself, as it represents a critical transition between general education and higher education, in addition to the specific aims associated with it. This has led many countries, including the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, to move toward revising and developing their curricula, in recognition of the central role curricula play in educating generations of learners and equipping them with the skills and knowledge needed for holistic personal growth and for advancing their societies.

Curriculum development has been defined by Al-Zand (2010) as a comprehensive process encompassing all curriculum elements and processes—from design, through implementation, to evaluation—as well as the factors that influence and are influenced by the curriculum, with the aim of improving, modifying, and changing these elements, stages, and factors.

Al-Khuli (2011) defined it as all steps, actions, and procedures through which the curriculum can be reformed and improved, beginning with a study of the current curriculum to identify its strengths and weaknesses and to translate its objectives into lived reality, in preparation for designing the necessary plans and programs to achieve these objectives.

Al-Sayyid et al. (2021) described it as a radical and comprehensive reconsideration of all curriculum components so that it keeps pace with new educational, organizational, cultural, scientific, and technological developments. Besbasi and Muhammad (2022) viewed it as all steps, actions, and procedures through which the curriculum can be reformed and improved, while Tamim (2025) defined it as improving, updating, and modifying the existing curriculum so that it becomes more suited to contemporary conditions and changes and more capable of achieving the intended objectives. Taken together, these definitions indicate that curriculum development rests on the continual reconsideration, updating, and improvement of instructional materials, objectives, teaching methods, and assessment strategies, in order to make them more effective, better aligned with students' and society's needs, and more responsive to scientific and technological developments, with the ultimate aim of preparing learners who are able to face the challenges of the age. 'Abd Al-Majid (2021) reinforces this view, noting that curriculum development is no longer limited to revisiting course topics by way of addition, deletion, modification, or rephrasing; rather, it has become an organized, purposeful, comprehensive, and ongoing process grounded in scientific, social, and economic studies and constitutes an inevitable necessity imposed by the nature of the contemporary era.

Reasons for Developing Secondary-School Curricula

Starting from the premise that school curricula are the effective tool societies use to build and shape the personalities of their members, and that they reflect these societies' aspirations, ambitions, and hopes for the future, many countries have undertaken broad and comprehensive revisions of their curricula. As a result,

they have achieved remarkable progress across various fields and at multiple levels (Al-Sherbini & Al-Tanawi, 2015).

- Addressing shortcomings in current curricula to raise their efficiency and effectiveness
- Enhancing international competitiveness by equipping students with future competencies and skills
- Responding to the intellectual, political, and economic implications of globalization by opening up to the world and benefiting from its positive aspects while preserving national identity
- Keeping pace with developments in the basic, psychological, social, and educational sciences
- Developing human resources capable of contributing to economic and social development
- Improving individual and collective performance quality and advancing comprehensive development
- Aligning the educational process with global progress through the internationalization of education
- Making curricula more closely connected to practical realities and future challenges
- Responding to changing concepts, attitudes, and interests resulting from rapidly evolving knowledge and communication technologies
- Taking into account the findings of educational research centers, as well as political, economic, and social transformations at local, regional, and international levels and anticipated future societal changes (Musa, 2020; 'A'llam, 2022; Delcker, 2023; Sha'ban, 2024)

In addition to these reasons, the present study holds that the desire to reform secondary-school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia stems from the country's status and its pursuit of leadership and international advancement in line with Vision 2030, as well as from the need to prepare graduates for higher education or entry into the labor market, expand and diversify learning opportunities, and strengthen values of citizenship and openness to the world.

Methods of Curriculum Development

A review of educational writings and previous research concerned with curriculum development shows that there are several methods for developing curricula, some traditional and others more recent, which can be summarized as follows:

Development by deletion: This involves removing content from the curriculum. Deletion may be partial, whereby part of the material is removed because it is unimportant, too difficult, inappropriate for students' level, or transferred to another grade. It may also be total, whereby an entire subject prescribed for a particular grade or stage is removed because it is deemed unimportant or unsuitable for students' level of maturity, or is shifted to a different stage (Bsbasi & Muhammad, 2022).

Development by addition: This means adding content to the curriculum and takes two forms. Partial development involves adding certain topics to a subject because of information gaps or in order to raise the level of the subject. Comprehensive development involves adding an entirely new subject to the curriculum for a specific grade or stage, for reasons such as the need for that subject or the desire to raise the overall level of the curriculum offerings.

Development by substitution: This entails changing the structure of a subject by replacing it with another structure—i.e., substituting some of the information or topics with other, similar topics in the curriculum, or revisiting existing content and revising it in line with new developments and current knowledge ('Isa, 2016).

Modern methods of development: These refer to approaches that take into account changes affecting the learner, the environment, society, culture, and contemporary educational theories. Many education systems have adopted such approaches by introducing pedagogical innovations that include educational activities, establishing scientific exhibitions and libraries, organizing recreational trips, setting up parent councils, awarding honors to outstanding students, issuing school ID cards, and utilizing students' suggestions in various areas in ways that foster their creativity and their desire to explore new methods (Al-Wakil, 2008).

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Commentary

The preceding discussion presented the theoretical framework of the study in two main axes. The first axis addressed the internationalization of education, which has become a central concern of global and local educational systems, as it aims to prepare leaders and global citizens by promoting intercultural understanding and linking students to global issues in ways that broaden their horizons and enable them to compete and confront the challenges of the twenty-first century. The second axis examined the development of school curricula, along with its reasons and imperatives, highlighting how curricula constitute the foundation for preparing learners for tomorrow—with all its ambitions and demands—within the broader international trend toward the internationalization of education.

Methodological Procedures of the Study

This section presents the methodological procedures adopted in the present study as follows:

1. Research Method In light of the topic of the present study and the nature of its variables, the descriptive-analytical method was selected as the most appropriate research design. The descriptive-analytical method, as explained by Al-Haim (2020), is a research approach that combines precise description of a phenomenon or problem with its analysis in order to identify its causes and the interrelated relationships among its variables.

The descriptive-analytical method takes two main forms: a qualitative form and a quantitative (numerical) form. The qualitative expression is used to describe the phenomenon and clarify its characteristics, whereas the quantitative expression provides a numerical description that indicates the magnitude of the phenomenon or its degree of association with other

phenomena.

2. Population of the Study The population of the study refers to the entire group of individuals, objects, or phenomena that share common characteristics and that the researcher is interested in studying in order to generalize the findings to them. It represents the broader framework from which the study sample is drawn (Obaidat et al., 2020). The population of the present study consisted of all secondary school teachers in Al-Kharj Governorate, whose total number reached 536 teachers. The researcher obtained the lists of public secondary schools and the numbers of teachers in them from the General Directorate of Education in Al-Kharj Governorate.

3. Sample of the Study The sample of the study is defined as a subset that is carefully selected from the research population (all individuals of the phenomenon) for the purpose of studying it and generalizing its results to the larger population. It constitutes an essential step in the research process and involves determining its size and the method of its selection to ensure the accuracy of the results and the saving of time and effort (Al-Assaf, 2017). The basic sample of the study was determined using Thompson's (2010) sample size equation, resulting in a sample of 110 teachers, who were selected from the population of secondary school teachers in Al-Kharj Governorate by means of simple random sampling, as shown in the subsequent table.

Table (1) Distribution of the study sample according to qualification and number of years of experience

Teachers by Qualification	Number	Percentage	Teachers by Qualification	Number	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	93	84.54	Less than 10 years	45	40.90
Postgraduate Studies	17	15.46	More than 10 years	65	59.10

4. Study Materials and Instruments:

A. Questionnaire: Internationalization of Education Topics in Secondary School Curricula

Objectives:

- Identify internationalization of education topics for secondary school curricula in KSA.

Steps for Developing the Questionnaire:

- Reviewed research and studies on internationalization of education.
- Reviewed educational literature on internationalization and international programs.
- Consulted education and academic experts.
- Reviewed secondary education objectives.
- Examined developmental characteristics and needs of secondary students.

In light of the above, an initial list was prepared of international topics that should be included in secondary stage curricula, comprising 7 main domains and 71 subtopics (with an eighth domain added later).

Main Domains:

- The ecosystem.
- Economic systems.
- Political systems.
- Shared human values.
- Global culture.
- International organizations.
- Pressing international issues.
- World history (added later).

Arbitration Process:

- Presented to 12 education specialists.
- Calculated importance level (%) for each topic.
- Topic accepted at 75% consensus.

In light of the results of the arbitration process, the researcher made several modifications suggested by the referees and excluded all topics that received an approval rating of less than 75%. Consequently, a finalized list of internationalization-of-education topics was obtained, along with the relative weight assigned to each topic, as shown in the following table.

Table (2) Topics of Internationalization of Education in its Final Form

No.	Axis	Subject	Percentage
1	Ecosystems	7	14%
2	Economic Systems	6	12%
3	Political Systems	5	10%
4	Shared Human Values	6	12%
5	Global Culture	7	14%
6	International Organizations	6	12%
7	Pressing international issues.	6	12%
8	World History	7	14%
Total		50 subjects	100%

b. Questionnaire to determine the extent to which internationalization of education topics are included in secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from teachers' perspectives:

The purpose of this questionnaire was to determine the extent to which internationalization of education topics are included in secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from the teachers' point of view. To develop this instrument, the researcher reviewed several previous studies and research related to the topic and solicited the views of several specialists through personal interviews, drawing on their input in formulating the questionnaire items.

In its initial form, the instrument comprised eight main domains: the ecosystem, economic systems, political systems, shared human values, global culture, international organizations, pressing international issues, and world history. These domains received a 100% approval rate from the panel of expert referees. The questionnaire included 50 topics related to the internationalization of education.

A three-point Likert scale was employed, consisting of three response options ranging from high to moderate to low. In parallel, the response level on the items was classified into three bands of relative weight as follows: items with a mean score between 1.00 and 1.66 were categorized as low, those with a mean between 1.67 and 2.33 were categorized as moderate, and those with a mean between 2.34 and 3.00 were categorized as high.

Establishing the validity and reliability of the instrument: The questionnaire was submitted to a panel of 12 experts specializing in curricula, teaching methods, measurement and evaluation, and secondary-school teaching to obtain their views on the questionnaire and the extent to which it validly measures what it was designed to measure.

Pilot administration of the questionnaire: The questionnaire was then administered to a pilot sample of secondary-school teachers in Al-Kharj, numbering 13 teachers, who were different from the main study sample. The results were subsequently coded and analyzed to determine the questionnaire's validity and reliability.

Internal consistency validity: To verify the internal consistency validity of the study instrument, Pearson's correlation coefficient was calculated between the score of each item and the total score of the instrument. The following table presents these results.

Table (3) Pearson's correlation coefficient for questionnaire items

Item	Correlation coefficient	Item	Correlation coefficient
1	0.740	26	0.814
2	0.810	27	0.777
3	0.716	28	0.750
4	0.732	29	0.901
5	0.840	30	0.870
6	0.837	31	0.752
7	0.880	32	0.834

8	0.805	33	0.860
9	0.710	34	0.740
10	0.742	35	0.814
11	0.840	36	0.912
12	0.880	37	0.903
13	0.880	38	0.780
14	0.844	39	0.880
15	0.829	40	0.910
16	0.903	41	0.807
17	0.870	42	0.846
18	0.810	43	0.740
19	0.829	44	0.860
20	0.810	45	0.912
21	0.780	46	0.904
22	0.901	47	0.870
23	0.810	48	0.845
24	0.752	49	0.770
25	0.901	50	0.764

The correlation coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). The results in the previous table indicate that all Pearson correlation coefficients between each item score and the total questionnaire score were statistically significant.

Instrument reliability: The reliability of the study instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The following table presents the instrument's reliability coefficients:

Table (4) Reliability coefficient of the instrument using Cronbach's alpha

No.	Axis	No. of Statements	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
1	Ecosystems	7	0.911
2	Economic Systems	6	0.840
3	Political Systems	5	0.903
4	Shared Human Values	6	0.880
5	Global Culture	7	0.780
6	International Organizations	6	0.890
7	Pressing international issues.	6	0.840
8	World History	7	0.912
	Overall Performance	50	0.869

The results presented in the previous table show that the reliability coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) for the questionnaire domains ranged between 0.780 and 0.912, while the overall reliability coefficient for the entire questionnaire reached 0.869, indicating high and acceptable internal consistency values. This suggests the questionnaire has a high degree of reliability. Accordingly, the questionnaire designed to determine the extent to which internationalization of education topics are included in secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from teachers' perspectives was adopted in its final form.

5. Statistical procedures used:

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the collected data. Descriptive statistical methods were employed, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, in addition to Cronbach's alpha test to compute the reliability of the research instrument and the independent-samples t-test.

6. Research variables: The study included the following variables:

Independent variables: secondary-school teachers categorized by:

- **Academic qualification:** Bachelor's degree and postgraduate studies
- **Years of experience:** less than 10 years and more than 10 years
- **Dependent variable:** responses to the questionnaire items.

7. Study procedures and data collection:

After finalizing the questionnaire, the researcher carried out the following procedures:

- The questionnaire was distributed to the main study sample of 110 teachers in secondary schools under Al-Kharj Education Directorate.
- The researcher clarified the questionnaire's purpose to teachers: a scientific study on internationalization of education topics in Saudi secondary curricula.
- Implementation began in the first semester of the 2025/2026 academic year.
- Data were collected and entered into SPSS for processing using appropriate statistical methods.

Presentation, discussion, and interpretation of the study results:

This section presents the findings derived from statistical analysis, aiming to answer the study questions. It also discusses and interprets these results in light of the theoretical framework and previous research.

1. Results for the first question: What are the internationalization of education topics for secondary school curricula in KSA?

The researcher developed a list of 8 domains with 71 topics. After arbitrator's review (75% consensus threshold), 8 domains with 50 topics were finalized.

2. Results for the second question: To what extent are these topics included in KSA secondary curricula (teachers' perspectives)?

A questionnaire (8 domains, 50 topics) was administered to 110 teachers. Means, SDs, and weighted means (Likert scale) were calculated.

Table (5) Means and Standard Deviations of the Degree of Inclusion of Internationalization of Education Topics in Secondary School Curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from Teachers' Perspectives (Sample Size = 110 Teachers)

No.	Topics of Education Internationalization	Overall Sample (n = 350)			
		Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Mastery Level	Item Rank
1	Ecosystems	2.28	0.827	Medium	2
2	Economic Systems	2.23	0.675	Medium	3
3	Political Systems	2.02	0.854	Medium	5
4	Shared Human Values	2.77	0.814	High	1
5	Global Culture	2.13	0.894	Medium	4
6	International Organizations	1.65	0.894	Low	8
7	Pressing international issues.	1.77	0.716	Medium	7
8	World History	1.89	0.839	Medium	6
Overall Performance		2.09	0.808	Medium	

It is evident from the previous table that:

- The weighted mean for the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula from teachers' perspectives was (2.09) with a standard deviation of (0.808), which is considered (moderate) according to the Likert scale.

- Topics of shared human values axes ranked first with a weighted mean of (2.77) and a standard deviation of (0.814), indicating a high level of inclusion.
- Topics of ecosystem axes ranked second with a weighted mean of (2.28) and a standard deviation of (0.827), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of economic systems axes ranked third with a weighted mean of (2.23) and a standard deviation of (0.675), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of global culture axes ranked fourth with a weighted mean of (2.13) and a standard deviation of (0.894), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of political systems axes ranked fifth with a weighted mean of (2.02) and a standard deviation of (0.854), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of world history axes ranked sixth with a weighted mean of (1.89) and a standard deviation of (0.839), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of pressing international issues axes ranked seventh with a weighted mean of (1.77) and a standard deviation of (0.716), indicating a moderate level of inclusion.
- Topics of international organizations axes ranked eighth with a weighted mean of (1.65) and a standard deviation of (0.894), indicating a low level of inclusion.

The reason for these results may be attributed to the tendency of secondary school curricula to focus on local issues and topics, as well as to societal traditions that may not regard teaching about the outside world as equally important. Moreover, there are cultural and social challenges, such as fear of innovation, an emphasis on localism at the expense of globalism, and concerns about the influence of other cultures, which may be perceived as a threat to local identity. These findings are consistent with several previous studies, such as Al-Nassar (2016), Al-Khalifa (2017), Al-Khateeb (2020), Al-Khath'ami (2022), Raslan (2022), Mohamed (2022), and Ali (2023).

3- Results related to the third question:

This question states: Are there statistically significant differences at the 0.05 level in the responses of the sample members regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula according to the variables of academic qualification and years of experience?

To answer this question, the following procedural steps were followed:

A- Academic qualification:

To determine whether there were statistically significant differences between the views of the study sample regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in the curricula attributable to the academic qualification variable, a comparison was made between the results of the group holding a Bachelor's degree and those of the group holding postgraduate degrees in the mean scores on the questionnaire. The independent-samples t-test was used to calculate the value of t for the difference between the mean scores of teachers on the questionnaire prepared for this purpose. The results are presented in the following table.

Table (6) t-test results for differences between the responses of the study sample regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula by academic qualification

Instrument	Qualification	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance Level
Questionnaire	Bachelor	93	2.24	0.821	1.09	0.273

	Postgraduate	17	2.27	0.816		
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The data in the above table indicate that there are no statistically significant differences at the 0.05 level in the responses of the sample members regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula according to the academic qualification variable. There was a clear convergence in the mean scores across the different academic qualifications, as the p-value was 0.109, which is greater than 0.05. This confirms that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample concerning the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula that can be attributed to the academic qualification variable.

This may be attributed to the fact that members of the study sample (Bachelor's and postgraduate degrees) possess similarly shared and convergent information and knowledge regarding the degree to which internationalization of education topics are included in the school curricula. This was reflected in the similarity of their responses on the questionnaire measuring the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula. In addition, these teachers undergo almost the same experiences and training programs provided by the Ministry of Education on school curricula and are similarly exposed to changes and developments introduced into the study programs.

B- Years of experience:

A comparison was made between the results of the study group whose members have less than 10 years of experience and the group whose members have more than 10 years of experience in the mean scores on the questionnaire measuring the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula. An independent samples t-test was used to calculate the t value for the difference between the mean scores of teachers with less than 10 years of experience and those with more than 10 years of experience on the questionnaire prepared for this purpose. The results are presented in the following table:

Table (7) Results of the t-test for the significance of differences between the responses of the study sample regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula according to the years-of-experience variable.

Instrument	Years of Experience	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Significance Level
Questionnaire	Less than 10 years	45	2.20	0.842	1.32	0.211
	More than 10 years	65	2.24	0.904		

The data in the above table indicate that there are no statistically significant differences at the 0.05 level in the responses of the sample members regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula that can be attributed to the years-of-experience variable. There was a clear convergence in the mean scores despite differences in the number of years of experience, as the p-value was 0.132, which is greater than 0.05. This confirms that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the responses of the study sample regarding the degree of inclusion of internationalization of education topics in secondary school curricula attributable to the years-of-experience variable.

This may be attributed to the fact that experience is not merely a matter of the number of years, but rather the accumulation of knowledge, skills, and diverse experiences that enable teachers to judge the quality of the curriculum, its ability to achieve its educational objectives, and its capacity to respond to both international and local requirements.

4. Results related to the fourth question, which states:

What is the proposed framework for integrating internationalization of education topics into secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia?

To answer this question, the following procedural steps were followed:

In light of the study results, which indicated that the degree to which internationalization of education topics are included in school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia was medium, the researcher proposes a framework for integrating these topics into secondary school curricula. This proposed framework comprises the following elements:

Definition of the proposed framework:

The proposed framework is a future-oriented plan developed in light of the findings of the present study, with the aim of establishing a general conceptual structure adopted by the researcher to guide the integration of internationalization of education topics into secondary school curricula in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Method used in constructing the proposed framework:

To construct the proposed framework, the constructivist approach was employed. This approach focuses on making the learner the centerpiece of the educational process by designing clear objectives, selecting coherent and meaningful content, using interactive teaching methods that emphasize self-construction of knowledge, designing practical activities connected to real-life situations, and implementing comprehensive assessment that focuses on skills and on linking prior knowledge with new information.

Foundations of the proposed framework:

The framework is built on two types of foundations:

First: Traditional foundations, which include:

Cognitive foundations: Related to the nature of knowledge and school subjects.

Psychological foundations: Related to the psychological characteristics, needs, and interests of secondary school students.

Social foundations: Related to societal problems, context, and issues.

Educational foundations: Related to organizing curriculum elements and the teaching-learning process within an integrated system extending from objectives to assessment.

Second: Requirements of the internationalization of education, which include:

Global integration: Linking the curriculum with global issues and challenges such as the environment, human rights, and cultural diversity.

Global competencies: Focusing on 21st-century skills, including critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration, creativity, and digital skills.

Flexibility and adaptability: Keeping pace with rapid changes and international standards.

Technology and digitization: Integrating technological tools, providing digital learning experiences, and using global learning resources.

Cultural diversity: Incorporating global perspectives and emphasizing understanding and respect of cultures and peaceful coexistence.

Lifelong learning: Building learners' capacity for continuous self-learning and autonomous knowledge acquisition.

International assessment: Employing modern assessment methods that measure skills and competencies, such as PISA.

Rationale for the proposed framework:

The findings of the present study, which highlighted the need to develop curricula in light of the global trend toward the internationalization of education.

The results and recommendations of previous research, which emphasized the need to develop secondary school curricula to align with contemporary requirements and the needs of local and international labor markets. Recommendations of international education, which call for building bridges of cooperation, respecting diversity, and preparing generations capable of living in global peace while preserving national identity. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's interest in secondary education under Vision 2030, which seeks to transform it into a system that keeps pace with contemporary developments by reforming curricula and linking them to the labor market. The need to activate the requirements of the internationalization of education within the educational process in order to keep up with modern educational trends and to achieve leadership, excellence, and competitiveness.

Premises of the proposed framework:

- The aspirations of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to elevate its educational system to a globally competitive level in light of Vision 2030.
- The general orientation of the Kingdom toward adopting systematic planning, scientific methodology, and future readiness across various sectors and fields, and toward formulating national development plans, particularly in the field of education.
- The need to develop school curricula in line with global trends in the internationalization of education.
- The need to incorporate global content that reflects worldwide knowledge developments across different disciplines.
- The need to integrate international cultures and experiences into school curricula to promote global understanding.
- The reality of the educational field, which reveals that learners need to acquire international skills that enhance their competitiveness.
- The need to address existing gaps in the field, particularly the gap between theoretical and practical aspects of learning.

Sources for constructing the proposed framework:

The proposed framework was developed in light of the findings of the present study and the analysis of the responses of the study sample regarding the degree to which internationalization of education topics are included in secondary school curricula. It also drew upon the results of related studies and research that addressed the internationalization of education; the features of secondary school curricula derived from the national strategy for developing pre-university education; successful international educational experiences; and the findings of comparative studies between Saudi curricula and those of some advanced countries, as well as global educational standards.

Objectives of the proposed framework:

The overall objective is to develop secondary school curricula focusing on internationalization of education topics. This includes cognitive, skill-based, and affective objectives tailored to each subject/course.

Content:**The framework covers 8 main domains with 50 topics:**

- Environmental system
- Economic systems
- Political systems
- Shared human values
- Global culture
- International organizations
- Pressing global issues
- World history

These topics are distributed balancedly across secondary school subjects.

Determining teaching strategies:

Several teaching strategies appropriate to the requirements of internationalization of education topics were proposed, including: problem-solving, inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, digital and blended learning, contextual learning, adaptive learning, cooperative learning and international online teams, and interactive learning.

Determining learning activities and instructional media:

The proposed framework incorporates a variety of activities suitable for internationalization of education topics, such as international research projects, exchange and training programs, field and exploratory trips, student journalism and debates, and cultural and intellectual activities. As for instructional media, it proposes digital platforms and distance learning, multimedia and interactive resources, virtual tours and simulations, digital collaboration tools, augmented and virtual reality, specialized websites, and learning platforms.

Determining assessment methods:

Assessment was proposed at its different stages ((formative, interim, and summative). The framework emphasizes the use of comprehensive assessment targeting the learner's performance across different educational domains, by employing modern assessment methods suitable for internationalization of education topics, such as electronic portfolios, performance-based assessment, self-assessment, peer assessment, standards-based assessment, and digital and interactive assessment.

Dimensions of the proposed framework:**1. Planning at the level of colleges of education:**

- Plan teacher prep programs based on competencies and future roles.
- Review and update courses to match global developments.
- Prepare teachers to implement and develop curricula effectively.
- Equip teachers with skills for labor market needs.
- Make research part of teacher prep for curriculum dev.
- Advance research to support curriculum dev and knowledge society.
- Provide training for novice teachers to boost competencies.

2. Training teachers and subject supervisors:

- Send teachers abroad for training to boost competencies.
- Train teachers on global developments and modern ed theories.
- Help teachers stay updated on curriculum design and dev.

- Develop guidelines for supervisors to activate modern teaching and assessment.
- Supervise teacher training by curriculum specialists.
- Design training programs for modern approaches in int'l education.
- Boost teachers' skills to link curricula to int'l ed requirements.

3. Teachers' performance in the educational field:

- Providing opportunities for teachers to acquire new knowledge and experiences in international education.
- Offering necessary support to teachers (time allocation, reduced teaching load, and fewer administrative tasks) to enable their participation in curriculum development.
- Encouraging collaborative practices and group discussions among teachers to exchange knowledge and experiences.
- Boosting teachers' morale in order to improve their efficiency, sense of satisfaction, and professional growth.
- Granting rewards to teachers with successful experiences in the internationalization of education.

The entities responsible for implementing the proposed framework include:

- The Ministry of Education in KSA.
- The various educational directorates.
- Educational districts within each directorate.
- Colleges of education in KSA.
- Secondary schools in KSA.

Mechanisms for implementing the proposed framework include:

- Approval by the Ministry of Education to implement the framework and directing relevant bodies.
- Providing necessary resources and materials.
- Allocating sufficient time and release time for those responsible.
- Ensuring adequate financial and human support.
- Promoting a culture of development among teachers.
- Implementing supportive procedures (workshops, discussion circles, training courses).

Recommendations of the study:

- Prepare teacher guides and incorporate international topics into curricula.
- Review and internationalize existing courses.
- Develop a strategic plan to support internationalization of secondary education.
- Use internationalization topics in assessing learners' performance.
- Implement the framework with secondary students and design for other stages.
- Ensure balanced distribution of topics across secondary grades.
- Enrich curricula with knowledge and skills for future jobs.
- Involve stakeholders in development and keep them informed.
- Adopt modern assessment methods aligning with internationalization.
- Train teachers in global education and modern methods.
- Develop teacher education programs for global citizenship.
- Organize training courses for curriculum planners.

Recommendations of the study:

- Preparing teacher guides and incorporating international topics into curricula.

- Reviewing and internationalizing existing courses.
- Developing a strategic plan to support internationalization of secondary education.
- Using the list of internationalization-of-education topics in assessing learners' performance.
- Implementing the proposed framework with secondary school students and designing a similar framework for other educational stages.
- Ensuring a balanced distribution of internationalization topics across secondary grade levels.
- Enriching secondary curricula with the knowledge and skills required for future jobs.
- Involving educational stakeholders in curriculum development and keeping relevant parties informed about updates.
- Adopting modern assessment methods that align with the internationalization of education.
- Training teachers in global education and modern teaching methods.
- Developing teacher education programs in colleges of education to foster concepts of global citizenship.
- Organizing training courses for those responsible for curriculum planning.

Proposed future research:

- Proposing a framework for developing secondary curricula in light of international understanding.
- Proposing a framework for developing teacher preparation programs to support internationalization of education.
- Implementing a program to develop global citizenship concepts among secondary students.
- Proposing a framework for developing secondary curricula in light of global sustainable development.
- Proposing a program to train secondary teachers in multilingual education.
- Conducting an evaluative study of secondary students' awareness of pressing global issues.

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